

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ROLE OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY IN FEMALE
INFERTILITY****Dr Hira Khalil¹, Dr. Maria Munir², Dr. Zulaikha Ayub³**¹Lahore General Hospital, Lahore, ²District Headquarters Hospital, Narowal, ³Fatima Jinnah Medical University Lahore.**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol) is the main form of vitamin D in the body. It is the form produced in the skin, and it can be found in some food and nutritional supplements. Prescription vitamin D is vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol).

Objectives of the study: The main objective of the study is to analyze the role of Vit-D deficiency in female infertility.

Methodology of the study: This cross sectional study was conducted at Lahore general hospital, Lahore during 2019. There were 70 females which was selected for study. By collecting data from these patients we find the role of Vit-D deficiency in female infertility. In these patients, levels of vitamin D were done. Out of total 70 infertile females, 45 were found to have VDD.

Results: In vitamin D deficient cases, the mean for vitamin D was higher and AMH was lower. In vitamin D deficient controls, the mean for vitamin D was 4.85 ± 3.02 and AMH was 3.47 ± 2.59 . On comparison, the vitamin D levels were lower in fertile than infertile females, which was significant.

Conclusion: There was no correlation found between VDD and AMH levels in both the infertile and fertile women groups. Prospective further studies are pressingly needed to confirm a causal relationship and to investigate the potential therapeutic benefits of vitamin D supplementation in this population.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Hira Khalil,**

Lahore General Hospital, Lahore.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Hira Khalil et al, **Role Of Vitamin D Deficiency In Female Infertility.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(09).

INTRODUCTION:

Vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol) is the main form of vitamin D in the body. It is the form produced in the skin, and it can be found in some food and nutritional supplements. Prescription vitamin D is vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol). In general, research shows that we metabolize vitamin D₃ more efficiently than vitamin D₂. Given enough time in the sun, most of us can make all the vitamin D we need. However, many women do not get enough sun exposure to maintain a normal vitamin D level throughout the year. Few foods are naturally rich in vitamin D, so it is also difficult to get enough vitamin D from your diet [1]. Other factors also affect vitamin D status. For instance, if you are overweight or have dark skin, you may be at risk for vitamin D deficiency. For these and other reasons, many women trying to conceive are likely to be low in vitamin D. Vitamin D has been linked to a variety of health benefits. For women trying to conceive, it appears to be linked to better fertility, as well as a healthy pregnancy [2]. Because of these potential benefits, SGF screens all female patients for vitamin D deficiency as part of their initial screening process. There are some studies showing that being vitamin D replete improves success rates in both in vitro fertilization (IVF) as well as transfer of frozen donor egg embryos. Other studies have not demonstrated that connection [3].”

Although the data for vitamin D and fertility is not conclusive, several studies have found that vitamin D blood levels of 30 ng/mL or higher are associated with higher pregnancy rates. Two studies found that among populations of mostly Caucasian and non-Hispanic white women, those with a normal vitamin D level were four times more likely to get pregnant through IVF compared to those who had a low vitamin D level [4]. Another study found that donor egg recipients with a normal vitamin D level had higher pregnancy rates than those with a low vitamin D level [5].

Many researchers have studied the role of vitamin D and its association with reproductive health extensively in the last few years but there is no single consensus on its influence in reproductive health. While it is a general observation that optimal level of vitamin D is essential in PCOS, endometriosis, male infertility and IVF techniques, but there has been no significant correlation between vitamin D levels and ovulation stimulation or embryo development and Vitamin D levels. However, larger studies including all ethnic and racial groups would be required to proclaim the role of Vitamin D in infertility [6].

Vitamin D, also known as “sunshine hormone”, is a fat soluble hormone which plays an integral part in calcium and phosphorous homeostasis and maintenance of healthy bones and teeth and is involved in providing protection against a number of diseases such as cancer, diabetes, multiple sclerosis, cardiovascular diseases, obesity and many other diseases including its role in infertility [7].

Objectives of the study:

The main objective of the study is to analyze the role of Vit-D deficiency in female infertility.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross sectional study was conducted at Lahore general hospital, Lahore during 2019. There were 70 females which was selected for study. By collecting data from these patients we find the role of Vit-D deficiency in female infertility. In these patients, levels of vitamin D were done. Out of total 70 infertile females, 45 were found to have VDD. Of these 35 patients were identified as cases; in whom, the AMH levels were assessed. In these patients, the AMH levels were assessed. The vitamin D levels were classified in three categories as deficiency, insufficiency, and sufficiency. The reference levels for serum (blood) of vitamin D [25(OH)D]: deficiency <10 ng/ml, insufficiency 10 to 20 ng/ml, and adequate levels were taken >20 ng/ml. The fertile females as control group, coming to our OPD for taking consultation due to other causes and normal working staff members were screened for vitamin D levels and who were found vitamin D deficient were enrolled as control. Age, duration of married life, duration and type of infertility, previous obstetrical history, and education levels were retrieved for all women who met the inclusion criteria as cases and control.

Vitamin D analysis:

Vitamin D levels were measured in duplicate using a Liasion 25OH vitamin D total assay (Randox Kit), using a competitive chemi luminescent immunoassay, as per the manufacturers guidelines.

Statistical analysis:

To analyze the correlation between vitamin D and AMH linear regression test and for comparison of both the groups, two sample *t* tests were used.

RESULTS:

Table 01 shows the demographic characteristics of patients and their SD with respect to data. Our study was done in infertile female’s population to see the spectrum of vitamin D levels. Overall, 64.28% infertile females had VDD (up to 10 ng/ml), 30.0%

displayed vitamin D insufficiency (10–20 ng/ml), whereas 5.71% of the study population exhibited adequate levels of vitamin D levels (>20 ng/ml).

Table 01: Demographic characteristics of participants.

Characteristics	Variables	S.D.
Females	28	-
Mean age in years (standard deviation)	43	14.2
Mean body mass index	29	-
Prevalence of hypertension	25%	-
Mid-upper arm circumference (in centimetres)	32	-
Duration of infertility	Upto 5 years > 5 years < 5 years	-

Table 3 of AMH ($P = 0.003$) but higher levels of vitamin D ($P = 0.04$) compared to fertile group in our study. However, no significant correlation was found between vitamin D and AMH levels in both the groups.

Table 02: Level of Vit-D in selected patients

Vitamin D levels	Infertile group (N = 70)	%
Deficient group (<10 ng/ml)	45	64.28
Insufficient (10–20 ng/ml)	21	30.0
Sufficient (>20 ng/ml)	4	5.71

Table 03: Mean value of Vit-D and AMH in control and infertile group

Mean value	Cases (infertile group)	Control (fertile group)
Vitamin D	6.18 ± 2.09 ng/ml ($P = 0.04$)*	4.85 ± 3.02 ng/ml
AMH	1.94 ± 1.30 ng/ml ($P = 0.003$)*	3.47 ± 2.59 ng/ml

AMH = antimullerian hormone; $P < 0.05$ by *t* test.

DISCUSSION:

Vitamin D is considered to be a prohormone and is synthesized by skin on exposure to sunlight as Vitamin D3 or cholecalciferol. Vitamin D2 or ergocalciferol is obtained from yeast and dietary sources [8]. Vitamin D deficiency can result from inadequate exposure to sunlight, malabsorption syndromes and certain drugs like dilantin, phenobarbitol and rifampicin which induce hepatic P450 enzymes to accelerate the catabolism of vitamin D [9].

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in studying the association of vitamin D deficiency and infertility. It has been postulated that vitamin D receptors (VDR) are found in human tissues such as male and female reproductive organs and play a major role in facilitating the biological activity of Vitamin D. In the US, it has been estimated that about one third of the population is deficient in Vitamin D and infertility affects nearly 15.5% of the US couples and nearly 53 million people all across the globe [10]. Vitamin D deficiency has been advocated as a possible cause of

infertility in many studies conducted in the past several years [11].

CONCLUSION:

There was no correlation found between VDD and AMH levels in both the infertile and fertile women groups. Prospective further studies are pressingly needed to confirm a causal relationship and to investigate the potential therapeutic benefits of vitamin D supplementation in this population.

REFERENCES:

1. Al-Jaroudi D, Al-Banyan N, Aljohani NJ, Kaddour O, Al-Tannir M. Vitamin D deficiency among subfertile women: case-control study. *Gynecol Endocrinol.* 2016;32:272–5.
2. Schoenaker DA, Jackson CA, Rowlands JV, Mishra GD. Socioeconomic position, lifestyle factors and age at natural menopause: a systematic review and meta-analyses of studies across six continents. *Int J Epidemiol.* 2014;43:1542–62.

3. Tal R, Seifer DB. Potential mechanisms for racial and ethnic differences in antimüllerian hormone and ovarian reserve. *Int J Endocrinol.* 2013;2013:818912.
4. Gold EB. The timing of the age at which natural menopause occurs. *Obstet Gynecol Clin North Am.* 2011;38:425–40.
5. Seifer DB, Golub ET, Lambert-Messerlian G, Benning L, Anastos K, Watts DH, et al. Variations in serum müllerian inhibiting substance between white, black, and Hispanic women. *Fertil Steril.* 2009;92:1674–8.
6. Wojtusik J, Johnson PA. Vitamin D regulates anti-Müllerian hormone expression in granulosa cells of the hen. *Biol Reprod.* 2012;86:91
7. Merhi ZO, Seifer DB, Weedon J, Adeyemi O, Holman S, Anastos K, et al. Circulating vitamin D correlates with serum antimüllerian hormone levels in late-reproductive-aged women: Women’s Interagency HIV study. *Fertil Steril.* 2012;98:228–34.
8. Bakhshalizadeh S, Amidi F, Alleyassin A, Soleimani M, Shirazi R, Shabani Nashtaei M. Modulation of steroidogenesis by vitamin D3 in granulosa cells of the mouse model of polycystic ovarian syndrome. *Syst Biol Reprod Med.* 2017;27:1–12.
9. Irani M, Merhi Z. Role of vitamin D in ovarian physiology and its implication in reproduction: a systematic review. *Fertil Steril.* 2014;102:460–68.
10. Feldman D, Pike JW, Glorieux FH. *Vitamin D.* 2nd ed. San Diego, CA: Elsevier Academic Press; 2005. pp. 15–36.
11. Durlinger AL, Gruijters MJ, Kramer P, Karels B, Ingraham HA, Nachtigal MW, et al. Anti-Müllerian hormone attenuates the effects of FSH on follicle development in the mouse ovary. *Endocrinology.* 2001;142:4891–9.